

Ozawa's inequality on the QCPB theory

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Abstract

With the non-universal validity of the QPB that has been replaced by the complete QCPB, as a result, we reconsider the Ozawa's inequality in light of the QCPB that improves the Ozawa's inequality and leads to some further useful results associated with the environment variable in the quantum geometric bracket. It certainly demonstrates a fact that environment coupling terms are unavoidable for the revision of the Ozawa's inequality under the perspective of the quantum geomertainty relation. More importantly, the modified Ozawa's inequality can greatly improve the quantum experimental precision, in this way, we can test and verify the validity of the quantum geomertainty relation.

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1 Introduction

The uncertainty principle historically introduced first in 1927, by Heisenberg [1], it states that the more precisely the position of some particle is determined, the less precisely its momentum can be known, and vice versa. The Heisenberg uncertainty relation for canonical observables position and momentum is certainly one of the most fundamental results in quantum mechanics. It was introduced by Heisenberg and mathematically proved by Kennard [2] and Weyl [3]. At present, the Heisenberg uncertainty relation has richly developed. Later on the Heisenberg uncertainty relation was generalized to the case of two arbitrary observables by Robertson [4,5] to extend the previous results to an arbitrary number of observables [6,7]. Then, Wang [8] has well proposed the QCPB equipped with quantum geometric bracket to study the Heisenberg uncertainty relation which have given a more complete result—the quantum geomertainty relation, and a series of complete interpretation of the quantum mechanics.

1.1 Formulations of the uncertainty principle

The Heisenberg was the first one to study the relation between the error and disturbance in quantum measurements. Supported by uncertainty principle, he derived a trade-off relation between the error $\epsilon(X)$ of the position measurement and the thereby caused momentum disturbance $\eta(P)$ given by [2,3]

$$\epsilon(X)\eta(P) \geq \hbar/2$$

However, by the development of the theory of quantum practical measurement, it was revealed that Heisenberg's relation does not generally hold.

Although, the Heisenberg's uncertainty principle has been known as one of the most fundamental principles in quantum mechanics. As the quantum mechanics developed, some unavoidable problems are exposed. Hence, it says that there is still ambiguity in formulation; So far, there has three classical different formulations to express the uncertainty principle. The Robertson uncertainty relation [4] is generally formulated as the relation

$$\sigma(A, \psi)\sigma(B, \psi) \geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2} \quad (1)$$

for any observables A, B and any state ψ , where the standard deviation $\sigma(X, \psi)$ of an observable X in state ψ is defined by

$$\sigma^2(X, \psi) = \langle \psi | X^2 | \psi \rangle - \langle \psi | X | \psi \rangle^2 \quad (2)$$

This relation was mathematically proven from fundamental postulates of quantum mechanics.

Heisenberg argued that the product of the noise in a position measurement and the momentum disturbance caused by that measurement should be no less than $\hbar/2$. This relation is generally formulated as follows: For any apparatus \mathbf{A} to measure an observable A , the relation

$$\epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A})\eta(B, \psi, \mathbf{A}) \geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2}$$

holds for any input state ψ and any observable B , where $\epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A})$ stands for the noise of the A measurement in state ψ using apparatus \mathbf{A} and $\eta(B, \psi, \mathbf{A})$ stands for the disturbance of B in state ψ caused by apparatus \mathbf{A} . Above relation is referred as the Heisenberg noise-disturbance uncertainty relation.

The Heisenberg uncertainty relation for joint measurements is generally formulated as follows: For any apparatus \mathbf{A} with two outputs for the joint measurement of A and B , the relation [5–7]

$$\epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A})\epsilon(B, \psi, \mathbf{A}) \geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2}$$

holds for any input state ψ , where $\epsilon(X, \psi, \mathbf{A})$ stands for the noise of the X measurement in state ψ using apparatus \mathbf{A} for $X = A, B$.

In 2003, Ozawa [7] derived the relation

$$\epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \sigma(A)\eta(B) \geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2}$$

holding for any pair of observables A, B and any measuring processes \mathbf{M} . Later, Branciard and Ozawa obtained a more stringent error-disturbance relation given by [7]

$$\begin{aligned} & \epsilon(A)^2\sigma(B)^2 + \sigma(A)^2\eta(B)^2 \\ & + 2\epsilon(A)\eta(B)\sqrt{\sigma(A)^2\sigma(B)^2 - D_{AB}^2} \geq D_{AB}^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $D_{AB} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr}(|\sqrt{\rho}[A, B]_{QPB}\sqrt{\rho}|)$. In the case where $A^2 = B^2 = \mathbb{I}$ and $M^2 = \mathbb{I}$, the above relation can be strengthened as

$$\hat{\epsilon}(A)^2 + \hat{\eta}(B)^2 + 2\hat{\epsilon}(A)\hat{\eta}(B)\sqrt{1 - D_{AB}^2} \geq D_{AB}^2$$

where $\hat{\epsilon}(X) = \epsilon(X)\sqrt{1 - \frac{\epsilon(X)^2}{4}}$ for $X = A, B$.

With the non-universal validity of the QPB that has been replaced by the complete QCPB. As a result, the QCPB [8] should be a substitute for all the QPB as a core in the error-disturbance uncertainty relation, that is a replacement given by

$$| \langle [A, B] \rangle | / 2 = \left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB} + G(s, A, B) \right\rangle \right| / 2$$

As it shown, the quantum geometric bracket $G(s, A, B)$ occupies a large proportion in the formula which naturally contains the environment variable. Recently, we have studied a revision of Heisenberg uncertainty relation based on environment variable in the QCPB theory [8], we have comprehensively and systematically gone through all uncertainty relations, by using the QCPB theory, we prove there exactly exists geometric entanglement term associated with the environment that cause the inevitable impact to the quantum measurement.

1.2 Ozawa's inequality

In this section, we briefly review how the Ozawa's inequality [7] derived, following its method to know some elementary knowledge is needed [see more details in [7]]. In order to clearly understand how the Ozawa's inequality deduced. In the beginning, some necessary symbols and knowledge are needed.

The error $\epsilon(A)$ of this measurement and the thereby caused disturbance $\eta(B)$ of an observable B of the system \mathbf{S} are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(A) &= \left\langle (A(0) - M(t_0))^2 \right\rangle_{\rho \otimes |\xi\rangle\langle\xi|}^{1/2} \\ \eta(B) &= \left\langle (B(0) - B(t_0))^2 \right\rangle_{\rho \otimes |\xi\rangle\langle\xi|}^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

where $t = 0$ is the time just before the measurement, $t = t_0$ is the time just after the measurement; Heisenberg operators at the above times are given by $A(0) = A \otimes \mathbb{I}$, $B(0) = B \otimes \mathbb{I}$, $M(t_0) = U^\dagger(\mathbb{I} \otimes M)U$, and $B(t_0) = U^\dagger(B \otimes \mathbb{I})U$, where U is a unitary operator. The noise $\epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A})$, or $\epsilon(A)$ for short, of the A measurement on input state ψ using apparatus \mathbf{A} is defined as the root-mean-square deviation of the experimental variable M out from the theoretical variable A^{in} , i.e.,

$$\epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A}) = \left\langle (M^{\text{out}} - A^{\text{in}})^2 \right\rangle^{1/2}$$

Then, it can prove that $\epsilon(A) = 0$ on any input state ψ if and only if apparatus \mathbf{A} measures observable A precisely. This ensures that precise apparatuses and noiseless apparatuses are equivalent. Let B be an observable of \mathbf{S} . The disturbance $\eta(B, \psi, \mathbf{A})$, or $\eta(B)$ for short, of observable B on input state ψ caused by apparatus \mathbf{A} is defined as the root-mean-square of the change in the observable B during the measuring interaction, i.e.,

$$\eta(B, \psi, \mathbf{A}) = \left\langle (B^{\text{out}} - B^{\text{in}})^2 \right\rangle^{1/2}$$

Then, it can prove that $\eta(B) = 0$ on any input state ψ if and only if apparatus \mathbf{A} does not change the probability distribution of the observable B , i.e., $\left\langle E^{B^{\text{in}}}(\Delta) \right\rangle =$

$\langle E^{B^{\text{out}}}(\Delta) \rangle$ for every interval Δ on any input state ψ . Thus, apparatuses not disturbing the observable B and apparatuses with zero disturbance, $\eta(B) \equiv 0$, are equivalent notions.

Under the above general definitions of noise and disturbance, it can rigorously investigate the validity of the Heisenberg noise-disturbance uncertainty relation, for this purpose, [7] has introduced the noise operator $N(A)$ and the disturbance operator $D(B)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} M^{\text{out}} &= A^{\text{in}} + N(A) \\ B^{\text{out}} &= B^{\text{in}} + D(B) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Since M and B are observables in different systems, then it has $[M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} = 0$, and hence the following commutation relation for the noise operator and the disturbance operator is obtained,

$$\begin{aligned} &[N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} + [A^{\text{in}}, D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &= -[A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Taking the modulus of means of the both sides and applying the triangular inequality, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} &|\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle| + \left| \langle [N(A), B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \rangle + \langle [A^{\text{in}}, D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle \right| \\ &\geq |\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle| \end{aligned}$$

Since the variance is not greater than the mean square, it has

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(A, \psi, \mathbf{A}) &\geq \sigma(N(A), \psi \otimes \sigma) \\ \eta(B, \psi, \mathbf{A}) &\geq \sigma(D(B), \psi \otimes \sigma) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and hence by the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, it has

$$\epsilon(A)\eta(B) \geq \frac{|\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle|}{2} \quad (6)$$

Thus, it yields the universally valid noise-disturbance uncertainty relation for the pair (A, B) ,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(A)\eta(B) &+ \frac{|\langle [N(A), B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \rangle + \langle [A^{\text{in}}, D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle|}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2} \end{aligned}$$

The above relation shows that the Heisenberg noise-disturbance uncertainty relation, holds if the correlation term $\left| \langle [N(A), B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \rangle + \langle [A^{\text{in}}, D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle \right|$ vanishes.

The universally valid uncertainty relation shows that for measurements of dependent intervention, the lower bound of the noise-disturbance product depends on the pre-measurement uncertainties of A and B . In order to obtain the trade-off among the noise $\epsilon(A)$, the disturbance $\eta(B)$, and the pre-measurement uncertainties $\sigma(A)$ and $\sigma(B)$, it applies the Heisenberg uncertainty principle to all terms in the left-hand-side of the universally valid noise-disturbance uncertainty relation. Then, the generalized noise-disturbance uncertainty relation is obtained by Ozawa,

$$\epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \sigma(A)\eta(B) \geq \frac{|\langle \psi | [A, B]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle|}{2} \quad (7)$$

also known as the Ozawa's inequality. The (7) holds for any apparatus \mathbf{A} specified by any probe state ξ , any unitary operator U , and any probe observable M , any observables A, B , and any input state ψ , and hence ultimately generalizes the Heisenberg noise-disturbance uncertainty relation to arbitrary measurements.

The most fundamental features of quantum mechanics is the existence of nontrivial error-disturbance relations given by the QPB for quantum measurements. In pace with discovering the QCPB as a complete theory to improve the QPB that has been self consistently and compatibly built for a complete description of the quantum mechanics. A series of changes about the QPB will follow for sure. Ozawa's inequality as the universally valid noise-disturbance uncertainty relation in quantum measurements holds by using the QPB, this will be the main topic we discuss in QCPB.

2 Generalized geometric commutator and geometric anticommutator

In this section, we shortly review some necessary concepts such as generalized geometric commutator and geometric anticommutator based on [8]. Let a and b be any two operators, their commutator is formally defined by $[a, b]_{cr} = ab - ba$. Let a and b be any elements of any algebra, or any operators, their generalized geometric commutator is formally defined by the following.

Definition 1 (GGC). [8] A generalized geometric commutator (GGC) of arity two a, b is formally given by

$$[a, b] = [a, b]_{cr} + G(s; a, b)$$

The geomutator is

$$G(s; a, b) = a[s, b]_{cr} - b[s, a]_{cr}$$

satisfying $G(s; a, b) = -G(s; b, a)$, where s is a geometric structure function given by domain.

Obviously, in some sense, the anticommutator also needs to be generalized as the commutator does, Analogously, denote by $\{a, b\}_{ir} = ab + ba$ the anticommutator,

Definition 2. [8] The geometric anticommutator (GAC) of any two elements a and b is defined by

$$\{a, b\} = \{a, b\}_{ir} + Z(s, a, b)$$

where $Z(s, a, b) = Z(s, b, a)$ is called anti-geomutator, s is geometric function.

As the definition above stated,

Definition 3. The anti-geomutator can be taken as

$$Z(s, a, b) = (a : s : b) + \{a, b\}_{ir}s$$

where $(a : s : b) = asb + bsa$, and s is the geometric function created by the environment.

Note that in order to preserve the related property of the anticommutator, we always let anti-geomutator $Z(s, a, b)$ satisfy the symmetry, namely, $Z(s, a, b) = Z(s, b, a)$. As a result of the symmetry of anti-geomutator, geometric anticommutator then follows the symmetry $\{a, b\} = \{b, a\}$. Actually, the anti-geomutator can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{aligned} Z(s, a, b) &= a\{s, b\}_{ir} + b\{s, a\}_{ir} \\ &= asb + bsa + abs + bas \\ &= (a : s : b) + \{a, b\}_{ir}s \end{aligned}$$

As seen, this form is very similar to the quantum geometric bracket, this is why we need to generalize the anticommutator.

2.1 The GGC and the GAC

In conclusions, the generalized geometric commutator (GGC) and the geometric anticommutator (GAC) can be listed as below [8]

The GGC and the GAC:

$$\begin{aligned} [a, b] &= [a, b]_{cr} + G(s, a, b), \\ \{a, b\} &= \{a, b\}_{ir} + Z(s, a, b), \end{aligned}$$

Meanwhile, the geomutator and anti-geomutator then follow

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, a, b) &= a[s, b]_{cr} - b[s, a]_{cr} \\ Z(s, a, b) &= a\{s, b\}_{ir} + b\{s, a\}_{ir} \end{aligned}$$

2.2 QCPB and quantum geobacket (QGB)

As [8] stated, the quantum covariant Poisson bracket (QCPB) is defined by generalized geometric commutator (GGC) while quantum geometric bracket (QGB) is given based on the geomutator. More precisely,

Definition 4 (QCPB). [8] *The QCPB is generally defined as*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{g} , where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$ is called quantum geometric bracket.

It is zero if and only if \hat{f} and \hat{g} covariant commute, i.e. $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$. It is remarkable to see that the QCPB representation admits a dynamical geometric bracket formula on the manifold. Note that structural function s represents the background property of spacetime.

It is believed that quantum mechanics is an incomplete description of reality. The QCPB suggests that hidden variables of certain types exist for a complete description of

physical reality. In particular, the quantum geometric bracket (QGB) which means that there exists hidden variables in the complete description such that quantum mechanics is complete.

Definition 5 (Quantum geometric bracket (QGB)). [8] *The quantum geometric bracket is*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

where s represents the globally condition of space.

Let's assert the role of the structure function s that is a geometric structure function given by domain based on the generalized geometric commutator, it means that structure function s is only determined by the environment, or spacetime, or manifolds, the domain, ect, from this viewpoint, the environment joins the physical process, the influence of the environment now based on new theory can't be ignored, it's naturally necessary to be considered in a physical process. In other words, the environment has joined the physical process, accordingly. By using the antisymmetric, the quantum geometric bracket (QGB) is rewritten as

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + \hat{g}[\hat{f}, s]_{QPB}$$

This expression can vividly and concretely state that the environment interacts with the operators \hat{f}, \hat{g} respectively.

Definition 6. *The covariant equilibrium equation is given by $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$, i.e.,*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = 0$$

for operators \hat{f}, \hat{g} .

Taking the modulus of means of the both sides

$$|\langle G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) \rangle| = |\langle [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} \rangle|$$

where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + \hat{g}[\hat{f}, s]_{QPB}$, and applying the triangular inequality, we have

$$|\langle \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} \rangle| + |\langle \hat{g}[\hat{f}, s]_{QPB} \rangle| \geq |\langle [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} \rangle|$$

2.3 Covariant dynamics, generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics

In this section, we will briefly review the entire theoretical framework of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket totally based on the paper [8]. More precisely, the time covariant evolution of any observable \hat{f} in the covariant dynamics is given by both the generalized Heisenberg equation of motion and G-dynamics.

Theorem 1. *The covariant dynamics, the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics can be formally formulated as*

The covariant dynamics: $\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]$

The generalized Heisenberg equation: $\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [f, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \hat{H} [s, f]_{QPB}$

G-dynamics: $\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$.

respectively, where $\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} + \hat{w}$ is covariant time operator, and \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ denotes the GGC of two operators.

As [8] stated, theorem 1 is a basic building material to construct a complete description of determinism of observables. As we can see clearly, the environment surely has a dynamical effects expressed by G-dynamics, it affirmatively can't be ignored, meanwhile, the generalized Heisenberg equation also states that the evolution of an observable is affected by the environment, in other words, the environment directly joins the quantum evolutionary process of any observables, it can be easily checked from the second part of the generalized Heisenberg equation.

3 Quantum geomertainty relation

In this section, we briefly review some concepts and results of the quantum geomertainty relation given by [8] for a better understanding of the Ozawa's inequality on the QCPB in the next section. In order to discuss easily, we write operator as $X = \hat{X}$.

3.1 The generalized variance and geoperator

Definition 7 (Geoperator). [8] *Let X be a Hermitian operator, then geoperator can be defined as*

$$X^{(s)} = X + u$$

where $u = Xs = I(X, s)$ is coupling interaction between the observable X and the environment s .

Obviously, the geometric operator is a extension of the Hermitian operator. Note that the interaction term $u = Xs = I(X, s) \neq 0$ actually is a precise function with respect to the spacetime, as we state, the structure function s generated by the space or manifolds as an environment variable only associate with the space or the manifolds, and it's independent to the wave function. The definition 7 can be called environmental coupling method, it evidently works, beautifully, seen from the paper [8].

According to (2), based upon the definition of variance, the generalized variance $\Sigma^2(X, \psi)$ of an observable X in state ψ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma^2(X, \psi) &= \langle \psi | X^{(s)2} | \psi \rangle - \langle \psi | X^{(s)} | \psi \rangle^2 \\ &= \langle \psi | (X + u)^2 | \psi \rangle - \langle \psi | (X + u) | \psi \rangle^2 \\ &= \langle \psi | X^2 | \psi \rangle - \langle \psi | X | \psi \rangle^2 + \rho(X, u) \\ &= \sigma^2(X, \psi) + \rho(X, s) \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where entanglement term $\rho(X, s)$ of an observable X in state ψ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\rho(X, s) &= \langle \psi | u^2 + Xu + uX | \psi \rangle - \langle \psi | u | \psi \rangle^2 - 2 \langle \psi | X | \psi \rangle \langle \psi | u | \psi \rangle \\ &= \sigma^2(u, \psi) - 2 \langle \psi | X | \psi \rangle \langle \psi | u | \psi \rangle + \langle \psi | \{X, u\}_{ir} | \psi \rangle\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

3.2 Geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality

The mean values for any observables can be alternatively expressed as $\langle X \rangle = \bar{X} = \langle \psi | X | \psi \rangle$. Let's always suppose that the Hermitian operator X is not an angle variable and Y is not the derivative in terms of this angle variable in this paper. And the $Y\psi$ is in the domain of the unbounded operator X in the most situations. With the non-universal validity of the QPB that is replaced by the complete QCPB, the corresponding is the universal formula given by geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality. Then we strictly prove geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality in quantum method as a generalization of the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality based on the Hermitian operator. It certainly demonstrates a fact that environment variable is unavoidable for the revision of the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality for the quantum mechanics. More precisely, it's mathematically shown as follows.

Theorem 2. [8] *Geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality is*

$$\Sigma^2(X, \psi) \Sigma^2(Y, \psi) = \Xi(s, X, Y) + \epsilon(s, X, Y)$$

for any Hermitian operator X and Y , where $\epsilon(s, X, Y) \geq 0$.

Proof. By using the geoperator in the definition 7, we define the generalized variance $\Sigma^2(X, \psi)$ (8) of an observable X in state ψ . In another way,

$$\Delta X^{(s)} = X^{(s)} - \overline{X^{(s)}} = \Delta X + \Delta u$$

and for $Y^{(s)}$, is written out explicitly as $\Delta Y^{(s)} = \Delta Y + \Delta v$, where $u = Xs$, $v = Ys$. Then it gets

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)} &= \Delta X \Delta Y + \Delta u \Delta Y + \Delta X \Delta v + \Delta u \Delta v \\ &= XY - \bar{X}Y - X\bar{Y} + \bar{X}\bar{Y} + uY - \bar{u}Y \\ &\quad - u\bar{Y} + \bar{u}\bar{Y} + Xv - \bar{X}v - X\bar{v} \\ &\quad + \bar{X}\bar{v} + uv - \bar{u}v - u\bar{v} + \bar{u}\bar{v}\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta Y^{(s)} \Delta X^{(s)} &= \Delta Y \Delta X + \Delta v \Delta X + \Delta Y \Delta u + \Delta v \Delta u \\ &= YX - \bar{Y}X - Y\bar{X} + \bar{Y}\bar{X} + vX - \bar{v}X \\ &\quad - v\bar{X} + \bar{v}\bar{X} + Yu - \bar{Y}u - Y\bar{u} \\ &\quad + \bar{Y}\bar{u} + vu - \bar{v}u - v\bar{u} + \bar{v}\bar{u}\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it yields

$$\left[\Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} = [X, Y] + 2[X, Y]_{QPB}^s$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \bar{Y}X + Y\bar{X} + \bar{v}X + v\bar{X} + \bar{Y}u + Y\bar{u} \\
& - \bar{X}Y - X\bar{Y} - \bar{u}Y - u\bar{Y} - \bar{X}v - X\bar{v}
\end{aligned}$$

where $[X, Y] = [X, Y]_{QPB} + G(s, X, Y)$ is the QCPB, and $G(s, X, Y) = \langle X : s : Y \rangle - [X, Y]_{QPB}^s$ is the quantum geometric bracket. Meanwhile,

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\{ \Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)} \right\}_{ir} &= \{X, Y\} + 2uv + 2\bar{X}\bar{Y} + 2\bar{u}\bar{Y} + 2\bar{X}\bar{v} + 2\bar{u}\bar{v} \\
& - \bar{X}Y - X\bar{Y} - \bar{u}Y - u\bar{Y} - \bar{X}v - X\bar{v} - \bar{u}v - u\bar{v} \\
& - \bar{Y}X - Y\bar{X} - \bar{v}X - v\bar{X} - \bar{Y}u - Y\bar{u} - \bar{v}u - v\bar{u}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\{X, Y\} = \{X, Y\}_{ir} + Z(s, X, Y)$ is the geometric anticommutator, $Z(s, X, Y) = \langle X : s : Y \rangle + \{X, Y\}_{ir}$ is the anti-geometator. It follows the expectation value in terms of the antisymmetric part

$$\begin{aligned}
& \langle \psi | \left[\Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} | \psi \rangle \\
& = \langle \psi | [X, Y] + 2[X, Y]_{QPB}^s | \psi \rangle \\
& = \overline{[X, Y]} + 2\overline{[X, Y]_{QPB}^s}
\end{aligned}$$

while the symmetric part is given by

$$\langle \psi | \left\{ \Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)} \right\}_{ir} | \psi \rangle = \overline{\{X, Y\}} + 2(\bar{u}\bar{v} - (\bar{Y} + \bar{v})(\bar{X} + \bar{u}))$$

Above all, we have

$$\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)} \right\}_{ir} + \sqrt{-1} \frac{[\Delta X^{(s)}, \Delta Y^{(s)}]_{QPB}}{2\sqrt{-1}}$$

As a result, for a simple form to show above result, we write

$$\overline{\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)}} = \left(\frac{\overline{\{X, Y\}}}{2} + \theta(s, X, Y) \right) + \sqrt{-1} \left(\frac{\overline{[X, Y]}}{2\sqrt{-1}} + \vartheta(s, X, Y) \right)$$

By letting

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta(s, X, Y) &= \bar{u}\bar{v} - (\bar{Y} + \bar{v})(\bar{X} + \bar{u}) \\
\vartheta(s, X, Y) &= -\sqrt{-1}[X, Y]_{QPB}^s
\end{aligned}$$

Then, it leads to module square

$$\left| \overline{\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)}} \right|^2 = \left(\frac{\overline{\{X, Y\}}}{2} + \theta(s, X, Y) \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\overline{[X, Y]}}{2\sqrt{-1}} + \vartheta(s, X, Y) \right)^2$$

Therefore,

$$\Sigma^2(X, \psi) \Sigma^2(Y, \psi) \geq \overline{\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)}}^2 \tag{10}$$

If we let $\Xi(s, X, Y) = \overline{\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)}}^2$, then geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality can be expressed as

$$\Sigma^2(X, \psi) \Sigma^2(Y, \psi) = \Xi(s, X, Y) + \epsilon(s, X, Y)$$

for any Hermitian operator X and Y , where $\epsilon(s, X, Y) \geq 0$, and the proof is completed. \square

The Schrödinger uncertainty relation is

$$\sigma_X^2 \sigma_Y^2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{2} \overline{\{X, Y\}}_{ir} - \bar{X} \bar{Y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{[X, Y]_{QPB}}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right)^2$$

Actually, it can be written as

$$\delta(X, Y) = \sigma_X^2 \sigma_Y^2 - \left(\frac{1}{2} \overline{\{X, Y\}}_{ir} - \bar{X} \bar{Y} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{[X, Y]_{QPB}}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right)^2$$

where $\delta(X, Y) \geq 0$. Hence, we can always get a certain expression of the $\delta(X, Y)$ based on the (10) with $\epsilon(s, X, Y)$, but in particular, if we let $\epsilon(s, X, Y) = 0$ be given, then $\delta(X, Y)$ has a specific formula.

3.3 Geometric entanglement term

Based on the generalized variance $\Sigma^2(X, \psi)$ of an observable X in state ψ , we give the concept of the geometric entanglement term as follows. According to (1), the product between the generalized variance $\Sigma^2(A, \psi)$ and $\Sigma^2(B, \psi)$ for any observables A, B and any state ψ is $\Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi)$ that generally formulated as [8]

$$\begin{aligned} & \Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi) \\ &= \sigma^2(A, \psi) \sigma^2(B, \psi) + \Theta(s, A, B) \end{aligned}$$

where the geometric entanglement term is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta(s, A, B) &= \rho(A, s) \sigma^2(B, \psi) \\ &+ \sigma^2(A, \psi) \rho(B, s) + \rho(A, s) \rho(B, s) \end{aligned}$$

It evidently says that the geometric entanglement term is the cause of the inevitability of environment. Hence,

$$\Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi) = \sigma^2(A, \psi) \sigma^2(B, \psi) + \Theta(s, A, B) \quad (11)$$

As a result of the complete expression given by (11) with the geometric entanglement term expressed as

$$\Theta(s, A, B) = \Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi) - \sigma^2(A, \psi) \sigma^2(B, \psi)$$

It implies that classic result $\sigma^2(A, \psi) \sigma^2(B, \psi)$ has to be revised to a new form including the environment variable $\Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi)$.

3.4 The QGR and entanglement term

Mathematically, the geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality 2 which contains the environment variable has been strictly proved for Hermitian operator, it states a fact that there are multiple entanglement term including the geometric entanglement term $\Theta(s, X, Y)$, and entanglement term $\rho(X, s)$, ect, this fact for a complete quantum theory is inevitable. Following geometric Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, then it naturally induces the case of the quantum geomertainty relation (QGR) given as follows.

Theorem 3 (Quantum Geomertainty Relation (QGR)). [8] *The variance between the operators A, B in a state satisfies*

$$\sigma_A^2 \sigma_B^2 + \Theta(s, A, B) = \Xi(s, A, B) + \epsilon(s, A, B)$$

where $\epsilon(s, A, B) \geq 0$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta(s, A, B) &= \rho(A, s) \sigma_B^2 + \sigma_A^2 \rho(B, s) + \rho(A, s) \rho(B, s) \\ \Xi(s, A, B) &= \left| \left(\frac{1}{2} \overline{\{A, B\}} + \theta(s, A, B) \right) \right|^2 + \left| \left(\frac{\overline{[A, B]}}{2\sqrt{-1}} + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right) \right|^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $[A, B]$ and $\{A, B\}$ are respectively the GGC and the GAC in terms of operators A, B , and the entanglement term is

$$\rho(X, s) = \sigma_u^2 - 2\bar{u}\bar{X} + \overline{\left\{ \hat{X}, u \right\}_{ir}} \quad (12)$$

for Hermitian operators $X = A, B$.

Obviously, the entanglement term (9) is equal to (12) in the theorem 3. In other words, the theorem 3 means that

$$\Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi) = \Xi(s, A, B) + \epsilon(s, A, B)$$

where $\epsilon(s, A, B) \geq 0$. Definitely, it's equivalent to the case

$$\Sigma^2(A, \psi) \Sigma^2(B, \psi) \geq \Xi(s, A, B)$$

In order to better understand this, we write it as [8]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^2(A, \psi) \sigma^2(B, \psi) + \Theta(s, A, B) & \quad (13) \\ & \geq \left| \left(\frac{\overline{[A, B]}}{2\sqrt{-1}} + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right) \right|^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Theta(s, A, B)$ is the geometric entanglement term. The inevitability of the environment is the most incisive to be reflected, it clearly states that the inevitability of environment always exists for the all quantum process.

Since we have $\Xi(s, X, Y) = \overline{\Delta X^{(s)} \Delta Y^{(s)}}$, as it can be seen, theoretically, owing to $\Sigma^2(X, \psi) \Sigma^2(Y, \psi)$ and $\Xi(s, X, Y)$ are all expressed as the certain formulae, it implies that

$$\epsilon(s, X, Y) = \Sigma^2(X, \psi) \Sigma^2(Y, \psi) - \Xi(s, X, Y)$$

can be precisely calculated, accordingly, where

$$\Sigma^2(X, \psi) = \sigma^2(X, \psi) + \rho(X, s)$$

is the generalized variance in terms of the observable X in state ψ .

4 Ozawa's inequality on the QCPB

In the guidance of the (13), obviously, this is a character for a right approximate theory, we will compatibly analyze the Ozawa's inequality by referring to this feature. In this sector, the QPB appeared in above different kinds of inequalities about the uncertainty principle will be replaced by the QCPB, we will see how it becomes more complete. we obtain the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation in QCPB for the pair (A, B) as an improvement of the Ozawa's inequality.

4.1 The QCPB in Ozawa's method

In this section, we directly substitute the QCPB into Ozawa's method. As we know, the QPB above should be replaced by the QCPB, hence, let's see how it becomes if we directly plug the QCPB into above equations by using the QPB. By substituting the QCPB into (4), then it turns to the form

$$[A^{in}, D(B)] + [N(A), B^{in}] + [N(A), D(B)] = -[A^{in}, B^{in}] \quad (14)$$

where $[\cdot, \cdot] = [\cdot, \cdot]_{QPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the QCPB. More precisely, it's shown as

$$\begin{aligned} & [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} \\ & + G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) + G(s, N(A), B^{in}) + G(s, N(A), D(B)) \\ & = -[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB} - G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the quantum geometric bracket in the (15) can be calculated respectively

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) &= A^{in}[s, D(B)]_{QPB} - D(B)[s, A^{in}]_{QPB} \\ &= A^{in}sD(B) - A^{in}D(B)s - D(B)sA^{in} + D(B)A^{in}s \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, N(A), B^{in}) &= N(A)[s, B^{in}]_{QPB} - B^{in}[s, N(A)]_{QPB} \\ &= N(A)sB^{in} - N(A)B^{in}s - B^{in}sN(A) + B^{in}N(A)s \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, N(A), D(B)) &= N(A)[s, D(B)]_{QPB} - D(B)[s, N(A)]_{QPB} \\ &= N(A)sD(B) - N(A)D(B)s \\ &\quad - D(B)sN(A) + D(B)N(A)s \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) &= A^{in}[s, B^{in}]_{QPB} - B^{in}[s, A^{in}]_{QPB} \\ &= A^{in}sB^{in} - A^{in}B^{in}s - B^{in}sA^{in} + B^{in}A^{in}s \end{aligned}$$

Let's denote $u = A^{in}s$, $v = B^{in}s$, and $\alpha = D(B)s$, $\beta = N(A)s$. Then the four quantum geometric brackets in the (15) can be simplified as

$$G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) = uD(B) - A^{in}\alpha - \alpha A^{in} + D(B)u$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G(s, N(A), B^{in}) &= \beta B^{in} - N(A)v - vN(A) + B^{in}\beta \\
G(s, N(A), D(B)) &= \beta D(B) - N(A)\alpha - \alpha N(A) + D(B)\beta \\
G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) &= uB^{in} - A^{in}v - vA^{in} + B^{in}u
\end{aligned}$$

As a result of the four quantum geometric brackets above, then it yields

$$\begin{aligned}
&G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) + G(s, N(A), B^{in}) \\
&\quad + G(s, N(A), D(B)) + G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) \\
&= \{u, D(B)\}_{ir} - \{A^{in}, \alpha\}_{ir} + \{B^{in}, \beta\}_{ir} - \{N(A), v\}_{ir} \\
&\quad + \{\beta, D(B)\}_{ir} - \{N(A), \alpha\}_{ir} + \{B^{in}, u\}_{ir} - \{A^{in}, v\}_{ir}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\}_{ir}$ is the anticommutator. Actually, it can be further simplified as

$$\begin{aligned}
&G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) + G(s, N(A), B^{in}) \\
&\quad + G(s, N(A), D(B)) + G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) \\
&= \{u + \beta, D(B) + B^{in}\}_{ir} - \{A^{in} + N(A), \alpha + v\}_{ir}
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, it's equal to

$$\begin{aligned}
&G(s, A^{in}, D(B)) + G(s, N(A), B^{in}) \\
&\quad + G(s, N(A), D(B)) + G(s, A^{in}, B^{in}) \\
&= \{M^{out}s, B^{out}\}_{ir} - \{B^{out}s, M^{out}\}_{ir}
\end{aligned}$$

where $u + \beta = M^{out}s$ and $\alpha + v = B^{out}s$ have been used. Then the (14) is equivalent to the form

$$\begin{aligned}
&[A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} + [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \\
&\quad + \{M^{out}s, B^{out}\}_{ir} - \{B^{out}s, M^{out}\}_{ir} = -[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The QCPB on Ozawa's method implies that the coupling interactions between the environment variable and observables expressed by $M^{out}s$ and $B^{out}s$. Following this character, we will address this issue systematically in next section.

4.2 Ozawa's inequality based on the environment variable

In order to naturally introduce the environment variable in the QCPB to the Ozawa's inequality, we have to consider the coupling of the environment variable that put impact on the observables. Firstly, the QPB in the Ozawa's inequality (7) should be naturally replaced by the QCPB, for this purpose, we will refer to the inequality (13) that leads us to a right approximation result for completing the Ozawa's inequality along with the environment variable. In other words, it means that a complete Ozawa's inequality should embody the right side of inequality (13).

As we can see from (3), the noise operator $N(A)$ is defined as the difference $M(\Delta t) - A(0)$ between the observable $A(0)$ to be measured and the meter observable $M(\Delta t)$ to be read and the disturbance operator $D(B)$ is defined as the change $B(\Delta t) - B(0)$ of B caused by the measuring interaction, i.e.

$$N(A) = M(\Delta t) - A(0)$$

$$D(B) = B(\Delta t) - B(0)$$

Note that the experimental variable M and the theoretical variable A^{in} are existed in an environment, then coupling interaction is unavoidable. Inspired by (16), it proclaims the existence of the coupling interactions $M^{\text{out}}s$ and $B^{\text{out}}s$, by this point, it strongly ask us to systematically generalize the observables and noise operator $N(A)$ and the disturbance operator $D(B)$ based on the definition 7 given by

$$\begin{aligned}\widetilde{M}^{\text{out}} &= M^{\text{out}} + u + \beta = M^{\text{out}} + M^{\text{out}}s \\ \widetilde{B}^{\text{out}} &= B^{\text{out}} + \alpha + v = B^{\text{out}} + B^{\text{out}}s\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

where we let $\Omega(A, s) = u + \beta = M^{\text{out}}s$, and $\mathcal{U}(B, s) = \alpha + v = B^{\text{out}}s$ be given to get the observables entangled with the environment, these are the representation of the interaction between the observables and the environment variable.

According to the definition 7, $\Omega(A, s)$ and $\mathcal{U}(B, s)$ represent the entanglement interactions between the observables and the environment. Since M and B are the observables in different systems, we also have $[\widetilde{M}^{\text{out}}, \widetilde{B}^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} = 0$, and hence we have the following commutation relation for the generalized noise operator and the generalized disturbance operator,

$$\begin{aligned}[\widetilde{M}^{\text{out}}, \widetilde{B}^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} &= [M^{\text{out}} + \Omega(A, s), B^{\text{out}} + \mathcal{U}(B, s)]_{QPB} \\ &= [M^{\text{out}} + A^{\text{in}}s + N(A)s, B^{\text{out}} + B^{\text{in}}s + D(B)s]_{QPB} \\ &= [M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} + [M^{\text{out}}, \mathcal{U}(B, s)]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [\Omega(A, s), B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB}\end{aligned}$$

where the first term is the classical result given by

$$\begin{aligned}[M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} &= [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [A^{\text{in}}, D(B)]_{QPB} + [A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB}\end{aligned}$$

This is rightly reflected by (4). As we can see, the left two parts are connected to the environment variable. Above commutation relation about $\widetilde{M}^{\text{out}}, \widetilde{B}^{\text{out}}$ can be denoted as

$$[\widetilde{M}^{\text{out}}, \widetilde{B}^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} = [M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} + \Gamma(s, A, B) = 0 \quad (18)$$

for simplicity, where entanglement interaction is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma(s, A, B) &= [M^{\text{out}}, \mathcal{U}(B, s)]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [\Omega(A, s), B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB}\end{aligned}$$

And each part of the $\Gamma(s, A, B)$ can be calculated respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}[M^{\text{out}}, \mathcal{U}(B, s)]_{QPB} &= [A^{\text{in}} + N(A), \alpha + v]_{QPB} \\ &= [A^{\text{in}}, v]_{QPB} + [A^{\text{in}}, \alpha]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [N(A), v]_{QPB} + [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB}\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} [\Omega(A, s), B^{out}]_{QPB} &= [u + \beta, B^{in} + D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &= [u, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \end{aligned}$$

and $[\Omega(A, s), \mathcal{U}(B, s)]_{QPB} = 0$, and entanglement interaction becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(s, A, B) &= [A^{in}, v]_{QPB} + [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [N(A), v]_{QPB} + [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [u, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \end{aligned}$$

Above all, plugging all computations into the (18) leads to the result

$$\begin{aligned} &[\widetilde{M}^{out}, \widetilde{B}^{out}]_{QPB} \\ &= [M^{out}, B^{out}]_{QPB} + \Gamma(s, A, B) \\ &= [A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} + [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [A^{in}, v]_{QPB} + [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} + [N(A), v]_{QPB} + [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} \\ &\quad + [u, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [u, D(B)]_{QPB} + [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} + [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \\ &= [A^{in}, B^{in}] + 2[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB}^s + e(A^{in}, D(B)) \\ &\quad + e(N(A), B^{in}) + e(N(A), D(B)) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$[A^{in}, B^{in}] = [A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB} + G(s, A^{in}, B^{in})$$

is the QCPB, and

$$\begin{aligned} e(A^{in}, D(B)) &= [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} + [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} + [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \\ e(N(A), B^{in}) &= [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} + [N(A), v]_{QPB} + [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} \\ e(N(A), D(B)) &= [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} + [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} + [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

As a result, the (18) rewrites

$$\begin{aligned} &e(A^{in}, D(B)) + e(N(A), B^{in}) + e(N(A), D(B)) \\ &\quad + [A^{in}, B^{in}] + 2[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB}^s = 0 \end{aligned}$$

In other words, furthermore, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} &e(A^{in}, D(B)) + e(N(A), B^{in}) + e(N(A), D(B)) \\ &= -[A^{in}, B^{in}] - 2[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB}^s \end{aligned}$$

Taking the modulus of means of the both sides for (19), accordingly, a series of inequalities follow

$$|\langle e(A^{in}, D(B)) \rangle| \leq \left| \langle [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} \rangle \right|$$

$$+ \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right|$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle e(N(A), B^{in}) \rangle| &\leq \left| \left\langle [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [N(A), v]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle e(N(A), D(B)) \rangle| &\leq \left| \left\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \end{aligned}$$

Applying the triangular inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &|\langle e(A^{in}, D(B)) \rangle| + |\langle e(N(A), B^{in}) \rangle| + |\langle e(N(A), D(B)) \rangle| \\ &\leq \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), v]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \end{aligned}$$

With above the triangular inequality, the inequality for (18) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \left\langle [A^{in}, B^{in}] + 2[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPB} s \right\rangle \right| \leq |\langle e(A^{in}, D(B)) \rangle| + |\langle e(N(A), B^{in}) \rangle| \quad (20) \\ &+ |\langle e(N(A), D(B)) \rangle| \\ &\leq \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), v]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [\beta, B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ &+ \left| \left\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), \alpha]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [\beta, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \end{aligned}$$

In order to obtain the trade-off among the noise $\epsilon(A)$, the disturbance $\eta(B)$, and the pre-measurement uncertainties $\sigma(A)$, $\sigma(B)$, and environment coupling interactions $\sigma(u)$, $\sigma(v)$, $\sigma(\alpha)$, $\sigma(\beta)$. Since the variance is not greater than the mean square, by using (5) and (6), (7). Then, we now obtain the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation in QCPB for the pair (A, B) ,

$$\begin{aligned} &\sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) \\ &+ \epsilon(A)\sigma(v) + \sigma(u)\eta(B) + \sigma(\beta)\sigma(B) + \sigma(\beta)\eta(B) \\ &+ \sigma(A)\sigma(\alpha) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(\alpha) \geq \frac{\left| \left\langle [A, B] + 2[A, B]_{QPB} s \right\rangle \right|}{2} \end{aligned}$$

where the QCPB is $[A, B] = [A, B]_{QPB} + G(s, A, B)$, and environment coupling terms are previously defined as $u = A^{in}s$, $v = B^{in}s$, and $\alpha = D(B)s$, $\beta = N(A)s$. Actually, above generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation is a complete

inequality when it comes to reflect the right side of the (13). In order to show it simply, it can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) \\ & + \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) \geq \frac{\left| \left\langle [A, B] + 2[A, B]_{QPBs} \right\rangle \right|}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

by using

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) &= \epsilon(A)\sigma(v) + \sigma(u)\eta(B) \\ &+ \sigma(\beta)\sigma(B) + \sigma(\beta)\eta(B) + \sigma(A)\sigma(\alpha) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

which can be treated as an entanglement term between the environment and the observables. As we can see, the geometric correction term is completely induced by the environment variable s , it richly says that the environment exerts its inescapable influence on the quantum measurements. More precisely, it can be shown in details as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) \\ & + \epsilon(A)\sigma(v) + \sigma(u)\eta(B) + \sigma(\beta)\sigma(B) + \sigma(\beta)\eta(B) \\ & + \sigma(A)\sigma(\alpha) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(\alpha) \geq \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right| \end{aligned}$$

where $\vartheta(s, A, B) = -\left\langle \sqrt{-1}[A, B]_{QPBs} \right\rangle$. Therefore, the above relation holds for any apparatus specified by any probe state, any unitary operator, and any probe observable, any observables A, B , and any input state, and hence eventually improves Ozawa's inequality, (7), to arbitrary measurements in a concrete environment s .

Definitely, the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation (21) achieved the character of (13) previously, it means that this is a complete form of the generalized noise-disturbance uncertainty relation. The above relation shows that the Heisenberg noise-disturbance uncertainty relation, holds if the correlation term

$$\sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon)$$

vanishes. Meanwhile, the above relation shows that the generalized noise-disturbance uncertainty relation holds if the geometric correlation term $\theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon)$ vanishes.

This valid generalized covariant uncertainty relation shows that the environment joins in for measurements of dependent intervention, the environment is inevitable to cause this uncertainty with the measurements seen from the right side of the equation (21), as previously stated, the lower bound of the noise-disturbance product totally depends on the pre-measurement uncertainties of A, B , and environment coupling terms $\Omega(A, s), \mathcal{U}(B, s)$. As a result, the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation in QCPB forms

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) \\ & \geq \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

This relation universally stands for the general quantum case in an environment represented by the environment variable s . To highlight the results of the generalized noise-disturbance uncertainty relation (7) given by Ozawa, the (22) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) \\ & \geq \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right| - \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence of the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation that is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} & \epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) + \theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) \\ & \geq \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right| \end{aligned}$$

We can see that it successfully achieves the goal we want, firstly, it improves the Ozawa's inequality in a specific environment more explicitly, secondly, it naturally deduces the QCPB in the right side to be compatible with the (13). Definitely, the environmental coupling method is a vital tool to realize how the environment interferes with the accuracy of quantum experimental data.

Obviously, there has another inequality followed as

$$\left| \frac{\langle [A, B] \rangle}{2} + \vartheta(s, A, B) \right| \leq \left| \frac{\langle [A, B] \rangle}{2} \right| + |\vartheta(s, A, B)|$$

by applying the triangular inequality. According to quantum geomertainty relation (QGR) expressed by theorem 3, the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation is still an approximate representation.

4.2.1 Special case one

Actually, for (17), if we let $\Omega(A, s) = u$, $\mathcal{U}(B, s) = v$ be considered for a simple case, in fact, this two terms unquestionably exist in reality for the quantum measurement according to the definition 7, then (20) correspondingly changes into a simple form

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, B^{in}] + 2[A^{in}, B^{in}]_{QPBS} \right\rangle \right| \\ & \leq \left| \left\langle [A^{in}, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), B^{in}]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [N(A), D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \left\langle [N(A), v]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| + \left| \left\langle [u, D(B)]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| \end{aligned}$$

Thusly, the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation becomes a simple form

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(B) \\ & + \sigma(u)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(v) \geq \frac{\left| \left\langle [A, B] + 2[A, B]_{QPBS} \right\rangle \right|}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it follows $\theta(s, A, B, \sigma, \eta, \epsilon) = \sigma(u)\eta(B) + \epsilon(A)\sigma(v)$, it means that $\sigma(\alpha), \sigma(\beta)$ all vanish. In this way, the accuracy and reliability of the experimental data are greatly improved.

4.2.2 Special case two

For the transformation (3), if we let the noise operator $N(A) = u$ and the disturbance operator $D(B) = v$ be given, in this case, it means the noise operator and disturbance operator are caused by the coupling interactions. Accordingly, as the perspective of the Ozawa, then (3) is shifted to the form

$$\begin{aligned} M^{\text{out}} &= A^{\text{in}} + u \\ B^{\text{out}} &= B^{\text{in}} + v \end{aligned}$$

Since M and B are observables in different systems, $[M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} = 0$ still holds, and hence we have the following commutation relation for the noise operator and the disturbance operator,

$$\begin{aligned} [M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} &= [A^{\text{in}} + u, B^{\text{in}} + v]_{QPB} \\ &= [A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} + [A^{\text{in}}, v]_{QPB} + [u, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB} \\ &= [A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}] + 2[A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB^s} \end{aligned}$$

Then $[M^{\text{out}}, B^{\text{out}}]_{QPB} = 0$ leads to $2[A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]_{QPB^s} = -[A^{\text{in}}, B^{\text{in}}]$. Then taking the modulus of means of the both sides,

$$\left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB^s} \right\rangle \right| = \frac{|\langle [A, B] \rangle|}{2} = \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle \right| \quad (23)$$

where $[\cdot, \cdot] = [\cdot, \cdot]_{QPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the QCPB. The (23) above also can be rewritten in the form

$$|\langle A : s : B \rangle| + \left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB^s} \right\rangle \right| \geq \left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right|$$

where $\langle A^{\text{in}} : s : B^{\text{in}} \rangle = uB^{\text{in}} - vA^{\text{in}}$, and since the inequality $|\langle A : s : B \rangle| \leq |\langle uB \rangle| + |\langle vA \rangle|$ holds, it leads to the result

$$\left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB} \right\rangle \right| - \left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB^s} \right\rangle \right| \leq |\langle uB - vA \rangle| \leq |\langle uB \rangle| + |\langle vA \rangle|$$

As a consequence, it yields

$$\left(\left| \left\langle [A, B]_{QPB^s} \right\rangle \right| + |\langle uB \rangle| + |\langle vA \rangle| \right) / 2 \geq \left| \left\langle \frac{[A, B]_{QPB}}{2\sqrt{-1}} \right\rangle \right|$$

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have proposed new covariant relations—generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation in QCPB for the pair (A, B) , for the trade-off between the measurement noise and disturbance with the environment that is also an approximate description. These relations demonstrates that the prevailing Ozawa's lower bound for the noise-disturbance product is valid for measurements without the intervention from the real environment variable. The measurement effect caused by environment has been always ignored, but new noise-disturbance uncertainty relation has nicely remedied this deficiency. As a further correction for the Ozawa's inequality

under the QCPB, the generalized covariant noise-disturbance uncertainty relation has further explains the inevitability of environmental variables. This new covariant relation can not only take us on a new insight for really realizing fundamental limitations on measurements set by quantum mechanics due to the environment variable, but also enhance the level of precision measurement if the environment is considered, it allows us to precisely get the measurement done with certainty.

To analyse prospects more rigorously about the quantum measurement, we have to employ the QCPB model. More accurate mathematical formulations around the QCPB are established for some conected problems by using environmental coupling method, it's to be even more accurate.

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